

SMARANDACHE DETERMINANT SEQUENCES

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In this note two types of Smarandache type determinant sequences are defined and studied.

(1) Smarandache Cyclic Determinant Sequences:

(a) Smarandache Cyclic Determinant Natural Sequence:

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1 \end{vmatrix}, \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2 \\ 2 & 1 \end{vmatrix}, \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 2 & 3 & 1 \\ 3 & 1 & 2 \end{vmatrix}, \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{vmatrix}, \dots$$

$$1, -3, -18, \dots, 160, \dots$$

This suggests the possibility of the n^{th} term as

$$T_n = (-1)^{[n/2]} \{(n+1)/2\} \cdot n^{n-1} \quad \text{--- (A)}$$

Where $[]$ stands for integer part

We verify this for $n = 5$, and the general case can be dealt with on similar lines.

$$T_5 = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 & 1 \\ 3 & 4 & 5 & 1 & 2 \\ 4 & 5 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 5 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \end{vmatrix}$$

on carrying out following elementary operations

(a) $R_1 =$ sum of all the rows, (b) taking 15 common from the first row

(c) Replacing C_k the k^{th} column by $C_k - C_1$, we get

$$T_5 = 15 \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 2 & 1 & 2 & 3 & -1 \\ 3 & 1 & 2 & -2 & -1 \\ 4 & 1 & -3 & -2 & -1 \\ 5 & -4 & -3 & -2 & -1 \end{vmatrix} = 15 \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & -1 \\ 1 & 2 & -2 & -1 \\ 1 & -3 & -2 & -1 \\ -4 & -3 & -2 & -1 \end{vmatrix}$$

$R_1 - R_2, R_3 - R_2, R_4 - R_2,$ gives

$$15 \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 & 5 & 0 \\ 1 & 2 & -2 & -1 \\ 0 & -5 & 0 & 0 \\ -5 & -5 & 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix} = 1875, \{ \text{the proposition (A) is verified to be true} \}$$

The proof for the general case though clumsy is based on similar lines.

Generalization:

This can be further generalized by considering an arithmetic progression with the first term as a and the common difference as d and we can define

Smarandache Cyclic Arithmetic determinant sequence as

$$\begin{vmatrix} a \end{vmatrix}, \begin{vmatrix} a & a+d \\ a+d & a \end{vmatrix}, \begin{vmatrix} a & a+d & a+2d \\ a+d & a+2d & a \\ a+2d & a & a+d \end{vmatrix}, \dots$$

Conjecture-1:

$$T_n = (-1)^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} S_n \cdot d^{n-1} \cdot n^{n-2} = (-1)^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} \cdot \{a + (n-1)d\} \cdot \{1/2\} \cdot \{nd\}^{n-1}$$

Where S_n is the sum of the first n terms of the AP

Open Problem: To develop a formula for the sum of n terms of the sequence.

(2) Smarandache Bisymmetric Determinant Sequences:

(a) Smarandache Bisymmetric Determinant Natural Sequence:

The determinants are symmetric along both the leading diagonals hence the name.

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1 \end{vmatrix}, \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2 \\ 2 & 1 \end{vmatrix}, \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 2 & 3 & 2 \\ 3 & 2 & 1 \end{vmatrix}, \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 3 \\ 3 & 4 & 3 & 2 \\ 4 & 3 & 2 & 1 \end{vmatrix}, \dots$$

$$1, -3, -12, \dots, 40, \dots$$

This suggests the possibility of the n^{th} term as

$$T_n = (-1)^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} \{n(n+1)\} \cdot 2^{n-3} \quad (\text{B})$$

We verify this for $n = 5$, and the general case can be dealt with on similar lines.

$$T_5 = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 & 4 \\ 3 & 4 & 5 & 4 & 3 \\ 4 & 5 & 4 & 3 & 2 \\ 5 & 4 & 3 & 2 & 1 \end{vmatrix}$$

on carrying out following elementary operations

(b) $R_1 = \text{sum of all the rows}$, (b) taking 15 common from the first row, we get

$$15 \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 2 \\ 1 & 2 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & -1 & -2 \\ -1 & -2 & -3 & -4 \end{vmatrix}$$

$R_1 = R_1 + R_4$ gives

$$15 \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -2 \\ 1 & 2 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & -1 & -2 \\ -1 & -2 & -3 & -4 \end{vmatrix} = 120, \text{ which confirms with (B)}$$

The proof of the general case can be based on similar lines.

Generalization: We can generalize this also in the same fashion by considering an arithmetic progression as follows:

$$\begin{vmatrix} a \end{vmatrix}, \begin{vmatrix} a & a+d \\ a+d & a \end{vmatrix}, \begin{vmatrix} a & a+d & a+2d \\ a+d & a+2d & a+d \\ a+2d & a+d & a \end{vmatrix}, \dots$$

Conjecture-2: The general term of the above sequence is given by

$$T_n = (-1)^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} \cdot \{ a + (n-1)d \} \cdot 2^{n-3} \cdot d^{n-1}$$